

THE UNION'S ACTION: REVIEWING THE MITIGATION OF THE UNITED STATES' ECONOMIC DECLINE DURING THE NOVEL CORONAVIRUS 2019 (COVID-19) PANDEMIC THROUGH FISCAL POLICIES

A Term Paper
Made in Partial Fulfillment
Of the Requirements in
Economics 101 (Macroeconomics)

ASISTIO, Acer Matthew S.
BERMUNDO, Marc Andrie M.
Proponents

Submitted to
Prof. Renz Venielle L. Lamayo, MAE
Economics 101 Course Instructor

Department of Economics and Political Science
College of Social Sciences
University of the Philippines Baguio

December 13, 2024

TABLE OF CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION	3
BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT	6
POLICY DESCRIPTION	10
Overview of the Policy	10
Implementation Timeline	11
Key Stakeholders	12
Funding / Mechanisms	13
POLICY ANALYSIS	10
Overview Analysis	15
Policy Weaknesses	17
Policy Strengths	18
Funding / Mechanisms	18
United Kingdom	18
Germany	20
CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	21
APPENDIX: LIST OF FIGURES USED	23
REFERENCES	29

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

The Novel Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic is one of the events that had the most severe global impact on recession in our history. It led to economies facing lockdowns and widespread business disruptions due to restrictions, causing a dramatic shift in the global economy in the year 2020. According to the International Monetary Fund (IMF), "It is very likely that this year the global economy will experience its worst recession since the Great Depression, surpassing that seen during the global financial crisis a decade ago. The Great Lockdown, as one might call it, is projected to "shrink global growth dramatically." (International Monetary Fund, 2020) Even with the expectation of a partial recovery in 2021, the IMF notes that global gross domestic product (GDP) will remain below pre-pandemic levels, with significant uncertainty surrounding the speed and intensity of the rebound. With the worsening of the crisis, government leaders worldwide implemented their respective fiscal and monetary policies to stabilize their economies, mitigate income losses, and serve as the main agents of economic recovery.

Figure 1: Graph showing the effect of changing government purchases or reduction in taxes. (Source: Mankiw, 2010)

Fiscal policy is crucial towards addressing economic downturns, decline, unemployment and other factors that relate to it. Governments often adjust spending and taxation to stabilize the economy in its optimal condition depending on the situation that influences key factors like national saving and investment. According to Mankiw, "A tax cut lowers T , raises disposable income $Y - T$, stimulates consumption, and reduces national saving. (Even though some of the tax cut finds its way into private savings, public saving falls

by the full amount of the tax cut; in total, saving falls.) Because $NX = S - I$, the reduction in national saving in turn lowers NX ." (Mankiw, 2010, p. 129) The S represents the **saving schedule**, I represents the **investment schedule**, NX represents the **net exports**, and Y represents **income or output**. Furthermore, based on the same figure, Mankiw states that "A fiscal policy change that increases private consumption C or public consumption G reduces national saving ($Y - C - G$) and, therefore, shifts the vertical line that represents saving from $S1$ to $S2$. Because NX is the distance between the saving schedule and the investment schedule at the world interest rate, this shift reduces NX . Hence, starting from balanced trade, a change in fiscal policy that reduces national savings leads to a trade deficit." (Mankiw, 2010, p. 129) This reduction in savings and the trade deficit can exacerbate unemployment, since the economy may face a reduction in investment and foreign exchanges. This will lead to limiting economic growth and recovery. This highlights the importance of fiscal policies that balance saving and investment. A trade deficiency will signal economic vulnerability, leading to a potentially reduced domestic investment and a slowdown in economic recovery. Through navigating proper national savings with the use of strategic fiscal responses, the government can stimulate investment and foster job creation, lessening the risk of unemployment and GDP stagnation.

In this paper, the proponents will examine the fiscal policy measures that were implemented by the United States during the height of the COVID-19 pandemic from 2020 to 2021. During this time, the U.S. government implemented numerous fiscal interventions to stabilize the economy. Some of these include the **Coronavirus Aid, Relief, and Economic Security (CARES) Act**, which provided direct cash transfers to households and individuals, expanded unemployment benefits, and initiated forgivable loans for small business enterprises with the **Paycheck Protection Program (PPP)**. Furthermore, government spending increased substantially to support the healthcare systems and state governments, while tax deferrals and credits were offered to lessen the burden of businesses and households. This analysis focuses on the efficiency and effectiveness of these measures in addressing difficult challenges in the economy, such as the rising unemployment rates, reduced consumer demand that leads to less consumer spending, and major disruptions and shutdowns in economic activity, be it big or small corporations, during the pandemic.

This paper will focus mainly on the fiscal policy measures that the United States had enacted during the height of the COVID-19 pandemic from the year 2020 up until 2021, the

peak of the COVID-19 pandemic. It will also delve into the interventions and strategies made by the government. It includes the CARES Act, the PPP, expanded unemployment benefits, and increased government spending towards healthcare and state support by giving cash. The policies mentioned were designed to maintain the economy in the most optimal condition possible by addressing rising unemployment, boosting consumer spending and demand, and mitigating the financial burdens faced by businesses and individuals. Simply put, this paper will provide an analysis of how U.S. fiscal policies mitigated the country's economic challenges posed by the pandemic as well as their implications for future economic resilience. The structure of this paper listed below, which will serve as the basis for analyzing U.S. policies:

1. **Introduction:** Give a background on the economic impact of the pandemic, highlighting the importance of fiscal responses that outline the focus of U.S. policies.
2. **Background and Context:** Examines the pre-pandemic condition of the United States and the disruptions caused by COVID-19 afterward, as well as the objectives of the fiscal policies.
3. **Policy Description:** Details of the specific fiscal policies, their implementation timelines, stakeholders, and funding process and mechanism.
4. **Policy Analysis:** Evaluates the effectiveness of the policies to highlight their strengths, challenges, and broader implications.
5. **Conclusion and Recommendations:** Summarizes the findings, discusses lessons learned, and offers recommendations for future use of policymaking in times of crisis.

CHAPTER 2

BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, the United States economy showed regional differences and variations in growth, reflecting an already decelerating trend after a decade of expansion since 2010 after the Great Recession. Based on what is stated earlier in the previous chapter, understanding these disparities is important for assessing the impact of fiscal responses during the pandemic.

Summary of Real Gross Domestic Product Growth

Region	2010-19	2018	2019
U.S.	2.3%	3.0%	2.2%
U.S. (Metro Portion)	2.3%	3.1%	2.1%
Eighth District	1.0%	1.7%	1.0%
Eighth District (Metro Portion)	1.1%	1.9%	1.1%
Largest Eighth District MSAs			
Little Rock, Ark.	0.7%	1.5%	0.9%
Louisville, Ky.	1.9%	1.7%	1.6%
Memphis, Tenn.	1.0%	2.0%	0.1%
St. Louis	0.7%	2.0%	1.0%
SOURCE: Bureau of Economic Analysis.			
NOTE: 2010-19 represents annual average growth rate.			

Figure 2: GDP growth in different regions. (Source: Bureau of Economic Analysis, 2020)

Regions across the U.S. experienced markedly different growth patterns during this period. “Counties in Western states, southern Texas, and Florida experienced the strongest growth in 2019, while the counties in the Midwest and northern Plains states experienced slower growth or contraction”. Additionally, the Metropolitan portion, which accounted for “about 90% of U.S. economic output,” saw growth decline “from 3.1% in 2018 to 2.1% in 2019”. However, approximately “10% of all metro areas reported growth rates above 4%,” with Midland, Texas, posting the fastest growth rate at 18.7% (Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, 2020).

The Eighth District, covering parts of the Midwest and South, exhibited growth below the national average, with an annual GDP increase of “just less than half the national rate at 1%, slowing from 1.7% in 2018”. Within this district, some areas faced severe economic contractions. For example, Pine Bluff, Arkansas, saw its GDP shrink by -1.6% in 2019, while

the metropolitan area of Fayetteville, Arkansas, experienced growth of only 0.6% (Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, 2020).

As the Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis highlights, “*most regions of the country follow a similar business cycle of expansion and contraction.*” However, differences in industry composition, legacy industries, demographics, or migration can amplify variations in economic outcomes. Between 2010 and 2019, almost one in five counties in the U.S. averaged negative economic growth, while just over 2% achieved double-digit growth at or above 10% (Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, 2020). This uneven performance, combined with state and local policy differences, magnified vulnerabilities ahead of the pandemic.

During 2020, attention shifted to “*state and county-level maps tracking the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic and reading news stories about how significantly different health and economic conditions appear from one region to the next.*” These structural variations are what had set the stage for the fiscal policies implemented in 2020 in response to the economic fallout caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The slowdown in real GDP growth in 2019 to an annual rate of 2.2%, coupled with significant regional disparities mainly due to differences in population size and economic policies, highlighted the pre-existing vulnerabilities of the U.S. economy before the pandemic. (Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, 2020)

The deceleration signaled a weakening strength in the national economy. This made it more challenging to withstand the shocks that occurred during the COVID-19 pandemic. As the structural disparities and regional dynamics already hindered consistent growth, these vulnerabilities magnified the pandemic’s negative impact. This is something that foreshadows a threat with an even bigger threat. This underscores the critical importance of targeted fiscal interventions to stabilize and rebuild the economy.

The onset of the COVID -19 pandemic in the early 2020 has resulted in a substantial number of disruptions to the U.S. economy, bringing about a rapid and unprecedented contraction in various sectors. The COVID-19 pandemic has been particularly damaging for small businesses, which represent most businesses in the United States and employ nearly half of all private sector workers (Bartik *et. al.*, 2020; Small Business Administration, 2012). By August 9, 2020, aggregate small business revenue across all industries had fallen by 19.1% compared to January 2020, with leisure and hospitality experiencing the steepest decline of

47.5%, followed by education and health services at 16.4 percent and retail and transportation at 14.1% (Bartik *et. al.*, 2020). This downturn was further exacerbated by the employees' inability to work remotely and the description of some sectors as non-essential, which caused them to face particularly poor outcomes.

These revenue declines corresponded with drastic job losses, especially among small businesses. Between March and April, employment in firms with fewer than 20 employees fell more than 16 percent; for firms with between 20 and 49 employees, the decline was 22 percent (Wilmot, 2020). Additionally, Small Business Pulse stated this statement: “Between August 30 and September 5, 50 percent of respondents had not rehired any employees, 5 percent of respondents had rehired at least one employee and 55 percent of respondents had not furloughed or laid off any employees.” (Small Business Pulse, 2020)

The broader economy also experienced record-breaking contractions. According to the National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER), “A peak in monthly economic activity occurred in the U.S. economy in February 2020, marking the end of the longest recorded U.S. expansion, which began in June 2009.” (NBER, n.d.) By the second quarter of 2020, real GDP suffered a decrease of 9.1 percent, the steepest quarterly drop since record-keeping began in 1947 (Routley, 2020). Compared to previous recessions, this contraction was unmatched, with GDP falling significantly more than the quarterly GDP drop of 3% recorded during earlier downturns (BEA, 2020a).

Source: U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis (BEA) 1990–2020; NBER n.d.; authors' calculations.
 Note: The figure shows the quarterly percent change in real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) from the peak of a business cycle until GDP returns to the level of the previous business cycle peak. GDP is in billions of chained 2012 dollars.

Figure 3: GDP changes (%) in different recessions. (Source: Bureau of Economic Analysis, 2020)

The pandemic's effects on employment were severe. As stated by the Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS), "Figure 4 shows the percent change in employment relative to business cycle peaks. COVID-19–related job losses wiped out 113 straight months of job growth, with total nonfarm employment falling by 20.5 million jobs in April." Furthermore, "COVID-19–related job losses wiped out 113 straight months of job growth, with total nonfarm employment falling by 20.5 million jobs in April." (BLS, 2020b; authors' calculations)

Source: Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS; Current Population Survey (CPS) 1980–2020; NBER n.d.; authors' calculations.
 Note: The figure shows the monthly percent change in total nonfarm payroll from the peak of a business cycle until total nonfarm payroll returns to the level of the previous business cycle peak.

THE HAMILTON PROJECT
 BROOKINGS

Figure 4: Percent change in unemployment. (Source: Bureau of Economic Analysis, 2020)

Finally, the decrease in total work hours in companies happened because of the layoffs of employees or being closed, rather than because the remaining employees worked fewer hours. According to Bauer, "The total number of hours worked fell by about 60 percent in March. While the number of daily hours began to rise again in mid-April, they leveled off at around 25 percent below baseline in June. Since then, aggregate hours have remained at between 25 and 30 percent of their baseline level." (Bauer et. al., 2020)

The U.S. government introduced fiscal policies to address the severe economic disruptions caused by COVID-19. This objective of these measures is to stabilize the economy, support small businesses, strengthen job protection, and provide immediate financial assistance and relief. Those policies sought to mitigate the effects of the deep recession, increase consumer goods and demand spending, and promote recovery, especially for vulnerable sectors and regions that are already facing economic challenges.

CHAPTER 3

POLICY DESCRIPTION

A. Overview of the Policy

At the height of COVID-19 pandemic, the U.S. government implemented various critical measures of fiscal policies to mitigate the economic downturn. Among the policies, the most significant were direct payments, unemployment insurance enhancements, and small business support initiatives such as the **Paycheck Protection Program (PPP)**. These measures were important towards addressing the financial strain faced by households and businesses.

Stimulus Payment Use	Response	Usage Rate
Food: <i>groceries, eating out, take out</i>	147,873,360	70.0%
Utilities and telecommunications: <i>natural gas, electricity, cable, internet, cellphone</i>	112,031,134	53.0%
Household supplies or personal care products	109,554,700	51.8%
Rent	61,122,424	28.9%
Vehicle payments: <i>scheduled or monthly</i>	54,203,300	25.6%
Mortgage: <i>scheduled or monthly</i>	52,728,740	24.9%
Paying down credit card, student loans, or other debts	49,691,147	23.5%
Clothing: <i>clothing, accessories, shoes</i>	38,539,666	18.2%
Savings or investments	29,144,718	13.8%
Household items: <i>TV, electronics, furniture, appliances</i>	14,146,362	6.7%
Other	11,935,561	5.6%
Charitable donations or giving to family members	10,456,404	4.9%
Recreational goods: <i>sports and fitness equipment, bicycles, toys, games</i>	5,681,344	2.7%
Did not report	436,306	0.2%
Total^a	211,338,876	

Figure 5: Stimulus Payment Use or Expected Use CRS tabulations of the Census Bureau’s Household Pulse survey for the week of July 9-14. (Source: Congressional Research Service, 2020)

Direct payments which are giving subsidies in the form of mainly cash were the foundation of the **Coronavirus Aid, Relief, and Economic Security (CARES) Act**. According to the Congressional Research Service (CRS), “*The maximum amount of these payments—sometimes referred to as ‘stimulus checks’ or ‘stimulus payments’—is \$1,200 per eligible individual (\$2,400 for married taxpayers filing a joint tax return) and \$500 per eligible child. The payment amounts are reduced by \$5 for each \$100 that a taxpayer’s income exceeds*

the phaseout threshold. These thresholds are (1) \$150,000, if filing as married filing jointly; (2) \$112,500, if filing as head of household; and (3) \$75,000, for single filers.” (Congressional Research Service, 2020a) This policy was outlined to quickly inject liquidity (money) into the economy by providing households and individuals with money to help with their financial needs.

This in turn will simultaneously stimulate the economy by mitigating the loss of consumer demand and spending or output. Shown above in Figure 5 is the tabular version of this statement by the CRS. Unemployment benefits were also expanded substantially by the CARES Act and was later passed down through the **American Rescue Plan Act (ARPA)**. Included were the **Federal Pandemic Unemployment Compensation or FPUC**, which provided an additional \$600 per week, later reduced to \$300 per week, on top of state benefits that were given. **Pandemic Unemployment Assistance (PUA)** also paves way for benefits being available to previously ineligible workers, such as gig economy workers and independent contractors to further broaden the number of people benefiting from it. *“ARPA extends the Continued Assistance Act’s reauthorization of FPUC at \$300 per week through weeks of unemployment ending on or before September 6, 2021. After September 4, 2021, no FPUC benefits are payable.”* (Congressional Research Service, 2021)

Moreover, the PPP has offered to give forgivable loans to small business owners to cover expenses such as payroll costs, rent, and utilities. These loans were crucial towards preventing layoffs by ensuring the continuity of business operations. The program’s success was measured by the ability to preserve jobs in various sectors that were the most vulnerable during the pandemic crisis.

B. Implementation Timeline

The implementation of fiscal measures followed a rapid timeline as the government sought to address the unfolding crisis. This timeline as shown in Figure 6 shows the swift and multi-phase approach taken by the U.S. government to stipulate both immediate relief and support in order to sustain the economy.

Date	Policy Measure
March 27, 2020	CARES Act enacted, including direct payments, PPP, and expanded unemployment benefits. (Source: Congressional Research Service, 2021)
April 2020	Distribution of the first round of stimulus checks began. (Source: Congressional Research Service, 2020a)
August 2020	Lost Wages Assistance provided \$300 per week in additional unemployment benefits. (Source: Congressional Research Service, 2021)
December 27, 2020	The Consolidated Appropriations Act extended Unemployment Insurance (UI) benefits and reauthorized PPP funding. (Source: Congressional Research Service, 2021)
March 11, 2021	ARPA enacted, extending benefits such as FPUC and introducing new provisions. (Source: Congressional Research Service, 2021)
September 2021	Expiration of ARPA's unemployment benefits, marking the end of major federal support programs. (Source: Congressional Research Service, 2021)

Figure 6: Implementation Timeline of the United States Government Policy Measures of the events in COVID-19 from March 2020 to September 2021. (Source: Congressional Research Service, 2021)

C. Key Stakeholders

The primary beneficiaries of these fiscal policies included:

1. **Households and Individuals:** Stimulus checks and enhanced unemployment benefits provided direct financial assistance. “*The Pulse Survey estimates that 211.3 million households (84.8%) have already received or expect to receive a stimulus payment.*” (Congressional Research Service, 2020a)
2. **Small Businesses:** Programs like the PPP that aimed to safeguard jobs and sustain business operations. Loans were distributed to businesses with less than 500 employees, on the condition that funds be used for payroll and essential expenses.
3. **Gig Workers and Independent Contractors:** Through the PUA program, individuals outside traditional employment structures received unemployment benefits for the first time. “*PUA is a temporary, federal UI program for individuals who are (1) not*

otherwise eligible for UI benefits (e.g., self-employed, independent contractors, gig economy workers); (2) unemployed due to a specific COVID-19-related reason; and (3) not able to telework and are not receiving any paid leave.” (Congressional Research Service, 2021).

4. **State Governments:** Federal funding supported state unemployment insurance systems and provided administrative funding to prevent fraud and ensure timely benefit distribution. “ARPA provides \$2 billion in additional UI administrative funding to DOL in FY2021 to ‘detect and prevent fraud, promote equitable access, and ensure the timely payment of benefits.’” (Congressional Research Service, 2021)

D. Funding / Mechanisms

The funding for these fiscal measures primarily relied on deficit spending and borrowing. The CARES Act and subsequent packages significantly increased federal debt but were considered necessary to prevent economic collapse. “ARPA provides \$2 billion in additional UI administrative funding to DOL in FY2021 to ‘detect and prevent fraud, promote equitable access, and ensure the timely payment of benefits.’” (Congressional Research Service, 2021)

Household Income Level	All Households	Percentage of All Households	Households That Received a Stimulus Payment ^a	Percentage of All Households That Received a Stimulus Payment	Percentage of Households by Household Income Level That Received a Stimulus Payment
Less than \$25,000	35,332,289	14.2%	30,773,112	14.6%	87.1%
\$25,000-\$34,999	26,802,457	10.8%	24,990,263	11.8%	93.2%
\$35,000-\$49,999	27,962,797	11.2%	26,067,884	12.3%	93.2%
\$50,000-\$74,999	38,774,009	15.6%	36,185,495	17.1%	93.3%
\$75,000-\$99,999	28,285,867	11.4%	26,315,108	12.5%	93.0%
\$100,000-\$149,999	30,532,645	12.3%	26,643,279	12.6%	87.3%
\$150,000-\$199,999	13,100,943	5.3%	9,780,316	4.6%	74.7%
\$200,000 and above	14,748,335	5.9%	4,285,223	2.0%	29.1%
Did not report	33,631,575	13.5%	26,298,197	12.4%	78.2%
Total	249,170,917	100.0%	211,338,877	100.0%	84.8%

Figure 7: Estimated Distribution of Stimulus Payment Recipients by Household Income Level CRS tabulations of the Census Bureau’s Household Pulse survey for the week of July 9-14.

(Source: Congressional Research Service, 2020)

Direct payments and PPP loans were funded through appropriations passed by Congress. The federal government’s ability to issue debt at historically low interest rates

facilitated the rapid mobilization of resources. “*The maximum amount of these payments—sometimes referred to as ‘stimulus checks’ or ‘stimulus payments’—is \$1,200 per eligible individual (\$2,400 for married taxpayers filing a joint tax return) and \$500 per eligible child.*” (Congressional Research Service, 2020a).

It can be said that the fiscal measures that were implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic presented a reflection of the comprehensive strategy done by the government to address immediate needs or concerns, sustain business operations, and lay the groundwork for economic recovery in the context of the United States Government.

CHAPTER 4

POLICY ANALYSIS

A. Overview Analysis

The fiscal policies implemented in response to the COVID-19 pandemic aimed to remedy the economic decline affecting the stakeholders such as the households and individuals, small businesses, gig workers, and independent contractors. After an initial decline due to the pandemic, retail sales in May 2020 rebounded 17.7% owing at least in part to the stimulus checks. Unemployment insurance enhancements played a similar role in supporting household consumption levels. Another major financial relief package for unemployed workers included a \$600 boost to state benefits from the Federal Pandemic Unemployment Compensation (FPUC) program which lessened the impact of their situation.

The expanded unemployment benefits also played a vital role in cushioning the labor market's blow. Unemployment peaked at 14.7% in April 2020 but fell to 6.7% by December 2020. Programs such as the Pandemic Unemployment Assistance (PUA) broadened coverage to gig workers and independent contractors, sectors traditionally excluded from unemployment benefits. This inclusivity ensured a wider safety net, reducing poverty rates by approximately 2.6 percentage points in 2020.

Figure 8: The United States Government Unemployment Insurance (UI) program recipients during 2020 to 2021, at the height of the COVID-19 pandemic. (Source: Spadafora, 2023)

The PPP also proved instrumental in preserving jobs and sustaining small businesses. By providing forgivable loans for payroll and essential expenses, the program helped keep unemployment in check. Data from the United States Small Business Administration (SBA) indicated that PPP loans preserved approximately 51 million jobs across various sectors. (Small

Business Administration, 2020) For example, the hospitality and retail industries, which were among the hardest hits, benefited significantly from PPP support. (Sabasteanski *et. al.*, 2022)

Figure 9: States relationship between Paycheck Protection Program (PPP) Loans and reopening orders of small businesses. (Source: Sabasteanski *et. al.*, 2022)

While some key sectors experienced cut-to-cut relief, the Americans found healthcare sector federal allocations that helped sustain operational activities despite revenue losses. Further, the construction and manufacturing sectors recovered better than anticipated due to the improved consumer spending driven by stimulus payments and PPP loans. However, sectors such as the travel and tourism (T&T) industry have expected longer recovery regimes due to the restrictions and inevitable absence of consumer confidence. (Orîndaru *et. al.*, 2021)

	T&T % of GDP		T&T GDP Change	Share of Total T&T Spending 2020		T&T Spending Change 2020 (%)	
	2020	2019	2020	Domestic	International	Domestic	International
USA	5.3↓	8.6	-41%	93.9	6.1	-37.1	-76.7
China	4.5↓	11.6	-59.9%	88	12	-60.8	-66.3
Japan	4.7↓	7.1	-37%	94.6	5.4	-30.3	-82.9
Germany	5.5↓	9.8	-46.9%	88.4	11.6	-47.3	-57.9
Italy	7↓	13.1	-51%	80.6	19.4	-49.6	-62
France	4.7↓	8.5	-48.8%	67.1	32.9	-49.8	-52.9
India	4.7↓	6.9	-36.3%	89	11	-30.7	-61
UK	4.2↓	10.1	-62.3%	85.4	14.6	-63.2	-71.6
Mexico	8.5↓	15	-48.1%	85	15	-48	-49.3
Australia	6↓	10.7	-45.4%	91	9	-41	-77.2
Brazil	5.5↓	7.7	-32.6%	94.4	5.6	-35.6	-39.1
Spain	5.9↓	14.1	-62.7%	63.2	36.8	-50.7	-78.2
Canada	3.2↓	6.4	-53%	81.2	18.8	-51	-71.1
Saudi Arabia	7.1↓	9.8	-38.8%	66.2	33.8	-30.9	-80.4
Russia	2.7↓	4.9	-47%	82.5	17.5	-43.9	-69.6
South Korea	2.4↓	4.4	-45.5%	67.9	32.1	-34	-68
Turkey	5↓	11	-54.2%	47.2	52.8	-41.8	-65.2
Indonesia	3.2↓	5.9	-46.6%	78.4	21.6	-35.2	-78.4
Argentina	6.5↓	9.4	-37.5%	91.7	8.3	-35.1	-66.7
South Africa	3.7↓	6.9	-49.8%	66.7	33.3	-42.8	-66

Figure 10: Indicators of the travel and tourism (T&T) industry for the year 2020. Highlighted in this figure is the percentage of the GDP of T&T went down to 5.5% and a drastic GDP contribution change of 41% for the United States, a member of the G20. (Source: Orîndaru *et. al.*, 2021)

B. Policy Weaknesses

The rapid rollout of the policies led to administrative hurdles including delays in processing unemployment claims, technical issues with state systems, and fraud concerns which hampered the effectiveness of unemployment benefits. For instance, some states struggled to distribute funds efficiently due to outdated IT infrastructure. Aside from this, PPP also received backlash. While it supported many businesses, critics argued that larger firms with more resources disproportionately benefited from the program. Data revealed that some publicly traded companies received substantial loans, sparking debates about equity in resource allocation.

Figure 11: Percentage distribution share of jobs lost, and loans distributed via the Paycheck Protection Program (PPP). (Source: Peter G. Peterson Foundation, 2020)

Certain sectors such as travel, and leisure did not benefit proportionately as well due to the nature of the pandemic's impact. While the policies provided broad economic support, targeted interventions for severely affected industries were limited. Additionally, Enhanced unemployment benefits, particularly the FPUC's \$600 weekly payments, faced criticism for potentially disincentivizing work. Although these payments were vital during the crisis, some argued that they created challenges for employers attempting to rehire workers. These policies significantly increased the federal deficit, raising concerns about long-term fiscal sustainability. By the end of 2020, the national debt had risen to over \$26 trillion, prompting debates about the trade-offs between short-term relief and long-term financial stability.

C. Policy Strengths

Despite its weaknesses, the fiscal measures of the U.S. Government demonstrated several strengths which helped alleviate the shock brought by the pandemic. Among them is the prompt delivery of relief on the households and businesses due to the quick enactment of the CARES Act and subsequent policies. The distribution of the first round of stimulus checks began within weeks of the CARES Act's passage, providing immediate financial support.

Policies like PUA also extended benefits to traditionally ineligible groups such as gig workers and independent contractors. This inclusivity marked a significant policy innovation and acknowledged the changing nature of the workforce. Additionally, the PPP's focus on payroll expenses successfully prevented mass layoffs. By the end of 2020, many small businesses reported improved confidence in their ability to sustain operations, reflecting the program's impact.

These policies effectively mitigated the economic downturn, with GDP rebounding by 33.4% in Q3 2020 after a historic contraction in Q2. Consumer spending, a critical driver of economic growth, remained resilient due to direct payments and enhanced unemployment benefits.

D. Comparison to Other Countries:

When compared to similar fiscal measures in other countries, the U.S. response showcased both strengths and areas for improvement.

United Kingdom

The UK implemented the **Coronavirus Job Retention Scheme (CJRS)**, a policy designed to prevent layoffs by directly subsidizing up to 80% of employee wages for businesses unable to operate during the pandemic. (GOV.UK, 2023) This measure ensured that workers remained attached to their employers even if they are temporarily furloughed. Through the direct covering of wage costs, CJRS minimized the administrative complexity often associated with loan-based programs like the PPP in the U.S. (Office for National Statistics, 2021) Unlike the PPP, which require businesses to apply for forgivable loans and meet specific criteria for loan forgiveness, the CJRS provided immediate relief through straightforward wage subsidies.

This approach not only alleviated financial pressures on businesses but also preserved job security for millions of workers, showcasing a highly efficient model for mitigating unemployment during economic crises. (Scottish Government, 2020)

Figure 12: Employment growth rates of high and low productivity firms, courtesy of the United Kingdom's CJRS. (Source: GOV.UK, 2023)

Figure 12: Employment growth rates of high and low productivity firms, courtesy of the United Kingdom's CJRS. (Source: GOV.UK, 2023)

Germany

Germany's *Kurzarbeit* program, a long-standing policy that allows reduced working hours with government-subsidized wages provided an efficient model for mitigating unemployment during the pandemic. Building on its established framework, *Kurzarbeit* offered a seamless transition into crisis management and minimized the need for new administrative systems. (International Monetary Fund, 2020) This pre-existing infrastructure enabled rapid deployment of support to affect businesses and workers. The program's design, which subsidized wages for reduced hours rather than providing lump-sum payments or loans, ensured that workers-maintained employment and businesses retained their skilled workforce. The *Kurzarbeit* program highlighted the advantages of proactive policy design, emphasizing the importance of having adaptable and scalable systems in place before crises occur. (Möller, 2010; CEPR, 2011) This foresight not only mitigated immediate unemployment but also positioned Germany for a smoother economic recovery by preserving employer-employee relationships and preventing long-term job losses.

Figure 13: Short- and long-term challenges facing the German economy and purchasing programs between neighboring countries as part of the Kuzarbelt program. (Source: German Council of Economic Experts, 2022)

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The fiscal measures implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic were instrumental in stabilizing the U.S. economy. These policies helped avert a deeper economic crisis by providing direct payments, expanding unemployment benefits and supporting small businesses. The swift rollout of these measures demonstrated the value of decisive action during an unprecedented emergency. Thus, despite challenges such as administrative inefficiencies, equity concerns, and the ballooning federal deficit, the overall effectiveness of these measures cannot be overlooked.

One of the key successes of these fiscal measures was their ability to cushion the economic blow for households and businesses. Direct payments provided immediate financial relief which allowed families to maintain consumption levels, contributing to a rapid rebound in retail sales. Expanded unemployment benefits such as those provided through the PUA and FPUC programs offered a lifeline to millions of workers including those in traditionally excluded sectors like gig work. This comprehensive safety net not only alleviated individual financial stress but also bolstered the economy by sustaining aggregate demand during a period of severe uncertainty.

Programs like PPP were also pivotal in preserving employment and ensuring business continuity. It prevented mass layoffs and supported approximately 51 million jobs across diverse industries by offering forgivable loans for payroll and essential expenses. While certain sectors like hospitality and retail saw significant benefits, others, such as travel and leisure, faced prolonged recovery challenges due to the nature of the pandemic's impact. The effectiveness of these measures highlights the importance of targeted support tailored to the unique needs of various economic sectors.

However, the rapid deployment of these policies also revealed significant weaknesses. Administrative hurdles, such as outdated IT systems and delays in processing unemployment claims, hampered the timely distribution of benefits. Equity concerns in resource allocation arose as larger in response to the disproportionate benefit that more resourceful firms gained from programs like the PPP. Furthermore, the enhanced unemployment benefits, while crucial for immediate relief, faced criticism for potentially disincentivizing work, complicating efforts to rehire workers as the economy began to recover.

The pandemic response also raised important questions about fiscal sustainability. By the end of 2020, the national debt prompted concerns about the long-term trade-offs between providing immediate relief and maintaining economic stability. This underscores the need for future policies to strike a careful balance between addressing short-term crises and safeguarding fiscal health. The experience highlights the importance of preemptive planning and the establishment of adaptable policy frameworks to mitigate the impact of future disruptions.

Lessons from other countries, such as the United Kingdom's CJRS and Germany's *Kurzarbeit* program also offer valuable insights. These models emphasized wage subsidies and maintained employer-employee relationships, providing examples of efficient and scalable solutions for minimizing unemployment and preserving economic stability. While the response of the United States is effective in many respects, it can benefit from incorporating such practices to enhance administrative efficiency and equity in future policy designs.

The experience of the COVID-19 fiscal response offers critical lessons for future policy development. Governments should aim for a balance between immediate relief and long-term fiscal sustainability. Enhancing administrative infrastructure to streamline benefit distribution and ensuring equitable resource allocation can improve the outcomes of similar measures. By learning from the successes and shortcomings of these policies, future responses to economic disruptions can be more inclusive, targeted, and effective. The pandemic highlighted the interconnectedness of economic resilience and social equity and emphasized the need for policies that address both dimensions in a holistic manner. Such an approach will be essential to navigating future challenges and fostering a more robust and equitable economy.

APPENDIX

LIST OF FIGURES USED

Figure 1: Graph showing the effect of changing government purchases or reduction in taxes. (Source: Mankiw, 2010)

Summary of Real Gross Domestic Product Growth

Region	2010-19	2018	2019
U.S.	2.3%	3.0%	2.2%
U.S. (Metro Portion)	2.3%	3.1%	2.1%
Eighth District	1.0%	1.7%	1.0%
Eighth District (Metro Portion)	1.1%	1.9%	1.1%
Largest Eighth District MSAs			
Little Rock, Ark.	0.7%	1.5%	0.9%
Louisville, Ky.	1.9%	1.7%	1.6%
Memphis, Tenn.	1.0%	2.0%	0.1%
St. Louis	0.7%	2.0%	1.0%

SOURCE: Bureau of Economic Analysis.
NOTE: 2010-19 represents annual average growth rate.

Figure 2: GDP growth in different regions. (Source: Bureau of Economic Analysis, 2020)

Figure 3: GDP changes (%) in different recessions. (Source: Bureau of Economic Analysis, 2020)

Source: Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS; Current Population Survey [CPS] 1980-2020; NBER n.d.; authors' calculations.
 Note: The figure shows the monthly percent change in total nonfarm payroll from the peak of a business cycle until total nonfarm payroll returns to the level of the previous business cycle peak.

Figure 4: Percent change in unemployment. (Source: Bureau of Economic Analysis, 2020)

Stimulus Payment Use	Response	Usage Rate
Food: groceries, eating out, take out	147,873,360	70.0%
Utilities and telecommunications: natural gas, electricity, cable, internet, cellphone	112,031,134	53.0%
Household supplies or personal care products	109,554,700	51.8%
Rent	61,122,424	28.9%
Vehicle payments: scheduled or monthly	54,203,300	25.6%
Mortgage: scheduled or monthly	52,728,740	24.9%
Paying down credit card, student loans, or other debts	49,691,147	23.5%
Clothing: clothing, accessories, shoes	38,539,666	18.2%
Savings or investments	29,144,718	13.8%
Household items: TV, electronics, furniture, appliances	14,146,362	6.7%
Other	11,935,561	5.6%
Charitable donations or giving to family members	10,456,404	4.9%
Recreational goods: sports and fitness equipment, bicycles, toys, games	5,681,344	2.7%
Did not report	436,306	0.2%
Total^a	211,338,876	

Figure 5: Stimulus Payment Use or Expected Use CRS tabulations of the Census Bureau's Household Pulse survey for the week of July 9-14. (Source: Congressional Research Service, 2020)

Date	Policy Measure
March 27, 2020	CARES Act enacted, including direct payments, PPP, and expanded unemployment benefits. (Source: Congressional Research Service, 2021)

April 2020	Distribution of the first round of stimulus checks began. <i>(Source: Congressional Research Service, 2020a)</i>
August 2020	Lost Wages Assistance provided \$300 per week in additional unemployment benefits. <i>(Source: Congressional Research Service, 2021)</i>
December 27, 2020	The Consolidated Appropriations Act extended Unemployment Insurance (UI) benefits and reauthorized PPP funding. <i>(Source: Congressional Research Service, 2021)</i>
March 11, 2021	ARPA enacted, extending benefits such as FPUC and introducing new provisions. <i>(Source: Congressional Research Service, 2021)</i>
September 2021	Expiration of ARPA's unemployment benefits, marking the end of major federal support programs. <i>(Source: Congressional Research Service, 2021)</i>

Figure 6: Implementation Timeline of the United States Government Policy Measures of the events in COVID-19 from March 2020 to September 2021. *(Source: Congressional Research Service, 2021)*

Household Income Level	All Households	Percentage of All Households	Households That Received a Stimulus Payment ^a	Percentage of All Households That Received a Stimulus Payment	Percentage of Households by Household Income Level That Received a Stimulus Payment
Less than \$25,000	35,332,289	14.2%	30,773,112	14.6%	87.1%
\$25,000-\$34,999	26,802,457	10.8%	24,990,263	11.8%	93.2%
\$35,000-\$49,999	27,962,797	11.2%	26,067,884	12.3%	93.2%
\$50,000-\$74,999	38,774,009	15.6%	36,185,495	17.1%	93.3%
\$75,000-\$99,999	28,285,867	11.4%	26,315,108	12.5%	93.0%
\$100,000-\$149,999	30,532,645	12.3%	26,643,279	12.6%	87.3%
\$150,000-\$199,999	13,100,943	5.3%	9,780,316	4.6%	74.7%
\$200,000 and above	14,748,335	5.9%	4,285,223	2.0%	29.1%
Did not report	33,631,575	13.5%	26,298,197	12.4%	78.2%
Total	249,170,917	100.0%	211,338,877	100.0%	84.8%

Figure 7: Estimated Distribution of Stimulus Payment Recipients by Household Income Level CRS tabulations of the Census Bureau's Household Pulse survey for the week of July 9-14. *(Source: Congressional Research Service, 2020)*

Figure 8: The United States Government Unemployment Insurance (UI) program recipients during 2020 to 2021, at the height of the COVID-19 pandemic. (Source: Spadafora, 2023)

Figure 9: States relationship between Paycheck Protection Program (PPP) Loans and reopening orders of small businesses. (Source: Sabasteanski et. al., 2022)

	T&T % of GDP		T&T GDP Change	Share of Total T&T Spending 2020		T&T Spending Change 2020 (%)	
	2020	2019		Domestic	International	Domestic	International
USA	5.3↓	8.6	-41%	93.9	6.1	-37.1	-76.7
China	4.5↓	11.6	-59.9%	88	12	-60.8	-66.3
Japan	4.7↓	7.1	-37%	94.6	5.4	-30.3	-82.9
Germany	5.5↓	9.8	-46.9%	88.4	11.6	-47.3	-57.9
Italy	7↓	13.1	-51%	80.6	19.4	-49.6	-62
France	4.7↓	8.5	-48.8%	67.1	32.9	-49.8	-52.9
India	4.7↓	6.9	-36.3%	89	11	-30.7	-61
UK	4.2↓	10.1	-62.3%	85.4	14.6	-63.2	-71.6
Mexico	8.5↓	15	-48.1%	85	15	-48	-49.3
Australia	6↓	10.7	-45.4%	91	9	-41	-77.2
Brazil	5.5↓	7.7	-32.6%	94.4	5.6	-35.6	-39.1
Spain	5.9↓	14.1	-62.7%	63.2	36.8	-50.7	-78.2
Canada	3.2↓	6.4	-53%	81.2	18.8	-51	-71.1
Saudi Arabia	7.1↓	9.8	-38.8%	66.2	33.8	-30.9	-80.4
Russia	2.7↓	4.9	-47%	82.5	17.5	-43.9	-69.6
South Korea	2.4↓	4.4	-45.5%	67.9	32.1	-34	-68
Turkey	5↓	11	-54.2%	47.2	52.8	-41.8	-65.2
Indonesia	3.2↓	5.9	-46.6%	78.4	21.6	-35.2	-78.4
Argentina	6.5↓	9.4	-37.5%	91.7	8.3	-35.1	-66.7
South Africa	3.7↓	6.9	-49.8%	66.7	33.3	-42.8	-66

Figure 10: Indicators of the travel and tourism (T&T) industry for the year 2020. Highlighted in this figure is the percentage of the GDP of T&T went down to 5.5% and a drastic GDP contribution change of 41% for the United States, a member of the G20. (Source: Orîndaru et. al., 2021)

Figure 11: Percentage distribution share of jobs lost, and loans distributed via the Paycheck Protection Program (PPP). (Source: Peter G. Peterson Foundation, 2020)

Figure 12: Employment growth rates of high and low productivity firms, courtesy of the United Kingdom's CJRS. (Source: GOV.UK, 2023)

Figure 12: Employment growth rates of high and low productivity firms, courtesy of the United Kingdom's CJRS. (Source: GOV.UK, 2023)

Figure 13: Short- and long-term challenges facing the German economy and purchasing programs between neighboring countries as part of the Kuzarbelt program. (Source: German Council of Economic Experts, 2022)

REFERENCES

“Annual Report 2021/22: SHAPING THE TRANSFORMATION: EDUCATION, DIGITALISATION AND SUSTAINABILITY.” n.d. German Council of Economic Experts. Accessed December 14, 2024. <https://www.sachverstaendigenrat-wirtschaft.de/en/annualreport-2021.html>.

“Comparison of Furloughed Jobs Data, UK - Office for National Statistics.” Accessed December 12, 2024. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/businessindustryandtrade/business/businessservices/articles/comparisonoffurloughedjobsdata/march2020tojune2021>.

“How Did the Fiscal Response to Coronavirus Help Small Businesses?” 2020. Peterson Foundation. October 23, 2020. <https://pgpf.org/article/how-did-the-fiscal-response-to-coronavirus-help-small-businesses/>.

“Modelling the Impact of Extending the CJRS.” Accessed December 12, 2024. <https://www.gov.scot/publications/covid-19-analysis-extending-coronavirus-job-retention-scheme/pages/5/>.

Bartik, Alexander W., Marianne Bertrand, Zoë B. Cullen, Edward L. Glaeser, Michael Luca, Bureau of Economic Analysis (BEA). 2020a. “Gross Domestic Product, 2nd Quarter 2020.”

Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS). 2020b. “Employment Situation Summary.”

CEPR. “The Roots of the German Miracle,” March 9, 2011. <https://cepr.org/voxeu/columns/roots-german-miracle>.

Christopher T. Stanton. 2020. "How Are Small Businesses Adjusting to COVID-19? Early Evidence from a Survey." *Brookings Institute*.

Bauer, Lauren, et al. "Ten Facts about COVID-19 and the U.S. Economy." The Hamilton Project, Brookings Institution, 2020.

Congressional Research Service. 2020a. "CARES Act Payments Use and Recipient Characteristics: In Brief." July 24, 2020. <https://crsreports.congress.gov>.

Congressional Research Service. 2021. "Unemployment Insurance Provisions in the American Rescue Plan Act of 2021." March 17, 2021. <https://crsreports.congress.gov>.

Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis. Economic Conditions Before COVID-19. June, 2020. <https://www.stlouisfed.org>

GOV.UK. "The Coronavirus Job Retention Scheme Final Evaluation." Accessed December 12, 2024. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-coronavirus-job-retention-scheme-final-evaluation/the-coronavirus-job-retention-scheme-final-evaluation>.

International Monetary Fund. *World Economic Outlook, April 2020: The Great Lockdown*. <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WEO/Issues/2020/04/14/weo-april-2020>.

Mankiw, N. Gregory. *Macroeconomics*. 7th ed. New York: Worth Publishers, 2010

Merkel, Christian, and Hermann Gartner. "The Roots of the German Miracle." Centre for Economic Policy Research. Centre for Economic Policy Research, March 9, 2011. <https://cepr.org/voxeu/columns/roots-german-miracle>.

Möller, Joachim. "Germany's Job Miracle in the World Recession—Shock-Absorbing Institutions in the Manufacturing Sector." *Applied Economics Quarterly (Formerly: Konjunkturpolitik)* 61, no. Supplement (2010): 9–28. https://ideas.repec.org/a/aeq/aeqaeq/v61_y2010_is_q5_p9-28.html.

National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER). n.d. "Business Cycle Dating Committee Announcements."

Orîndaru, Andreea, Maria-Floriana Popescu, Alina Petronela Alexoaei, Ștefan-Claudiu Căescu, Margareta Stela Florescu, and Anca-Olguța Orzan. 2021. "Tourism in a Post-COVID-19 Era: Sustainable Strategies for Industry's Recovery." *Sustainability* 13 (12): 6781. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13126781>.

Papanikolaou, Dimitris, and Lawrence D. Schmidt. 2020. "Working Paper on Remote Work Challenges."

Routley, Nick. 2020. "Historical Drops in GDP in the U.S." *Visual Capitalist*.

Sabasteanski, Nika, Jeremy Brooks, and Thomas Chandler. 2021. "Saving Lives and Livelihoods: The Paycheck Protection Program and Its Efficacy." *Economia* 22 (3): 278–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econ.2021.11.004>.

Small Business Administration. 2012. "Small Business Economic Impact."

Small Business Pulse. 2020. "Survey Results on Rehiring Patterns."

Spadafora, Francesco. 2023. "U.S. Unemployment Insurance through the Covid-19 Crisis." *Journal of Government and Economics* 9:100069. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jge.2023.100069>.

Stevenson, Betsey. 2020. "COVID-19's Employment Impact on Women." Washington, D.C.: International Monetary Fund, 2020.